

Short communication

First record of *Chinavia acuta* (Dallas, 1851) (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) in Cape Verde

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Abstract. This paper presents the first record of *Chinavia acuta* in the Cape Verde archipelago.

Key words: Hemiptera, true bugs, stink bug, faunistics, distribution, new records.

Cape Verde is an island country in the central Atlantic Ocean. The archipelago is situated about 650 kilometres west of Senegal. The climate of Cape Verde is characterized by particularly low rainfall but relatively high humidity (Chevalier 1935; Schmutterer et al. 1978). Together with the Azores, Canary Islands, Madeira, and the Savage Islands, Cape Verde forms part of the Macaronesia ecoregion (Lindberg 1958).

The first information about true bugs occurring in Cape Verde appeared in the work of Bergroth (1893), who listed eight species collected on these islands that were deposited in a museum in Lisbon. He also noted that the hemipteran fauna of Cape Verde was completely unknown. A much broader study, presenting a list of over 150 heteropteran species from this archipelago, was carried out half a century later (Lindberg 1958). It is worth mentioning that Lindberg's work was preceded by studies on the archipelago's flora (Chevalier 1935).

In the second half of the twentieth century, information about true bugs from Cape Verde also appeared in several papers. For example, Wagner (1957) described a new species (*Aethus lindbergi*), Schmutterer et al. (1978) discussed a native crop pest affected by drought, while Grimm and Führer (1998) monitored phytophagous bugs feeding on *Jatropha curcas* L. The final list of animals and plants found on the Cape Verde archipelago was published fifteen years ago (Báez et al. 2005).

The genus *Chinavia* Orian was established in 1965 to include nine species from the Afrotropical region, but since then its taxonomic status has been confused. Linnavouri (1972) placed *Chinavia* as a synonym of *Acrosternum*, then later (1982) he elevated it to subgenus status. This was followed by Rolston (1983) in

his studies of the New World species. More recently, Schwertner (2005) treated *Chinavia* as a full, valid genus, which has been followed in the subsequent papers (e.g. Grazia et al. 2006; Genevicius & Schwertner 2014; Genevicius et al. 2017; Servino & Schwertner 2020) again.

Chinavia represents a very common group of green stink bugs, medium in size, which are distributed in the Afrotropical, Nearctic and Neotropical regions. Polyphagous in habit, they have been recorded on host plants of more than 30 families (Grazia et al. 2006). Some species are pests of important crops, e.g. *Chinavia acuta* (Dallas, 1851) in tropical Africa (Couilloud 1989; Egonyu et al. 2005).

Chinavia acuta is a completely green species. Each humeral angle of the pronotum is produced into a prominent spine. It feeds on various cultivated plants and weeds (Servino & Schwertner 2020). When breeding, the milky white eggs are laid primarily on the upper sides of leaves in small clusters of up to 50. The larvae are black from the moment of hatching and remain grouped on the empty eggshells. During their development, the colouring of the larvae is highly variable and can differ from that of adults (Poutouli et al. 2011).

A few other similar species of *Chinavia* are often found on cultivated plants, but only one more African species has the spinose humeral angles: *Chinavia dispar* (Schouteden, 1960). However, they are easily distinguished, because the humeral spines in *C. dispar* have a yellow colour, while in *C. acuta*, red (Fig. 1) (Servino & Schwertner 2020).

One adult male of *C. acuta* was caught on January 16, 2020, on the island of Sal. This is the first record of this species on the islands of Cape Verde.

Fig. 1. *Chinavia acuta*: male collected on Sal island (photo by G. Gierlasiński).

Material examined

Cape Verde: 1 adult male (Fig. 1), 16.01.2020, Sal island, Santa Maria (gps: 16.600111, -22.908969), leg. D. Kojder, det. G. Gierlasiński, ver. D.A. Rider.

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